

**XXVIII INTERNATIONAL SYMPOSIUM ON
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IN GEODESY AND RELATED FIELDS**

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**GEOSPATIAL MODELLING INSIDE THE „ORLOVA CHUKA”
CAVE IN BULGARIA**

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ABSTRACT

“Orlova chuka” – the second largest cave in Bulgaria – is located in the “Rusenski Lom” Nature Park. Its current explored length of 14 km consists of a labyrinth of intertwining galleries and chambers, some of which are home to large colonies of bats. Being of significant importance for bat research for years, in the summer of 2018 the cave hosted a project, aimed at research of bats’ sophisticated echolocation capabilities. The project involved the mounting of 20 microphones and other recording equipment inside a chamber at the entrance of the cave. The XYZ coordinates of the microphones were to be determined with sub-centimeter accuracy in a local coordinate system. The research also required a 3D spatial model of this chamber and its adjacent galleries. This was performed via terrestrial laser scanning. Several mesh models with different detail depth were obtained from 11 full-resolution co-registered point clouds. The project provided an adequate base for further interdisciplinary activities between the geospatial and biological scientific fields.

1. BIOLOGICAL MOTIVATION FOR THE WORK: THE COCKTAIL PARTY NIGHTMARE

Bats are the only flying mammals that are active in the night as they fly large distances in search of food and shelter. Their echolocation system enables many bats to fly in complete darkness without colliding with the objects in their surroundings. These fascinating creatures have been the topic of an active and growing field of research for the past fifty years as more and more is discovered about their special sensory capability (Fenton, 2013; Simmons & Gaudette, 2012). Echolocating bats perceive their surroundings by emitting loud sounds and listening for the echoes that reflect off objects in their surroundings. Using the delayed arrival time, intensity and spectral characteristics of the returning echo, they are able to form an ‘auditory scene’ of the obstacles, conspecifics and prey around them. A host of primarily laboratory based studies with trained bats have created a comprehensive understanding about echolocation as a sensory modality (Fay, 2012), and a developing market for consumer-grade audio equipment is now promoting investigations of how they echolocate under progressively natural conditions.

Echolocating bats navigate by hearing the returning echoes of environmental objects. However, these echoes can sometimes be relatively faint, and bats might not be able to hear them, particularly when they are overlapped by another, loud sound. This is analogous to the human situation of trying

to follow a conversation in the midst of other loud sounds in a social gathering or music concert, called the ‘cocktail party problem’(Bee & Michey, 2008; Cherry, 1953). This leads to the prediction that echolocating bats may then tend to avoid sources of such loud sounds as it interferes with echo perception. However, many echolocating bats regularly echolocate under what seems to be the most challenging conditions for echo reception - in the presence of other bats, and within reverberant environments such as caves. Echolocation in a group is expected to be very challenging for bats because each individual bat emits calls as loud as a jack hammer (100-120dB SPL re 20 μ Pa at 1 m distance to the mouth) at ten times a second (Fenton, 2013). When multiple bats fly in the same space together, the problem of being able to hear object echoes is expected to increase non-linearly (Lin & Abaid, 2015). This is called the ‘cocktail party nightmare’ (Moss & Surlykke, 2010). Despite the theoretically expected problems, most species of bats are very social and engage in group flight, prey capture and mating behaviors (Ortega, 2016). The mechanisms that facilitate echolocation while flying in groups are still only poorly understood.

Figure 1. Multiple bats flying the recording chamber in the cave as recorded by the thermal cameras. The bright orange spots in the frame are the bats. The colour legend shows the temperature scale in degrees Celsius.

Figure 2. The multichannel audio recording system spanning the recording volume. Microphones were attached to the inverted-T shaped array and to the wall (left of the array, see cables). Photo credit: Stefan Greif

We investigated the ‘cocktail party nightmare’ by using non-intrusive acoustic and video recordings to understand how individual bats are capable of echolocating in the presence of multiple conspecifics in their natural environment. Flight room experiments to date have always studied group echolocation behavior in pairs of bats or with speaker playbacks (Amichai, Blumrosen, & Yovel, 2015; K. Fawcett, Jacobs, Surlykke, & Ratcliffe, 2015; Kayleigh Fawcett & Ratcliffe, 2015; Luo, Goerlitz, Brumm, & Wiegrebe, 2015). To date only few studies have investigated how bats echolocate in groups in the wild (Cvikel, Egert Berg, et al., 2015; Cvikel, Levin, et al., 2015; Lin, Abaid, & Müller, 2016), and this is a growing area that we seek to advance with the use of in-situ multi-channel audio and video recordings. Orlova Chuka cave, our field site, hosts a large summer population of *Myotis myotis* and *Myotis blythii* bats and thus presents a unique opportunity to study the cocktail party nightmare with many bats flying inside the cave. Bats roost in the interior of the cave, and are active around sunset in the corridors leading to one exit, moving in and out through this exit over multiple hours each night.

Echolocating bats have been studied in their natural settings through acoustic tracking with multiple microphone arrays (Aubauer, 1994; Goerlitz, Ter Hofstede, Zeale, Jones, & Holderied, 2010; Hügel et al., 2017; L. Jakobsen & Surlykke, 2010; Lewanzik & Goerlitz, 2018; Seibert, Koblitz, Denzinger, & Schnitzler, 2015). Each call arrives at a microphone at a slightly different time, allowing a precise calculation of the bat’s 3D-position for each emitted call, given a set of known microphone positions. Linking multiple successive 3D-positions, the flight trajectory of a bat can be stitched together. Multiple microphones not only allow the acoustic tracking of bats, but also the measurement of source level (Goerlitz et al., 2010; Lewanzik & Goerlitz, 2018; Seibert et al., 2015) and beam shapes (Lasse Jakobsen, Ratcliffe, & Surlykke, 2013; Seibert et al., 2015). While now even consumer grade electronics allow the assembly of multiple channel recording systems, the hurdle of precisely measuring the exact geometry of the microphone array still remains, particularly when not using fixed array geometries, but instead positioning the microphones onto natural surfaces in the bats’ environments. Errors in estimation of microphone geometry can lead to erroneous estimates (Plinge, Jacob, Haeb-umbach, & Fink, 2016) of bat position and sound source parameters, and thus it is essential to obtain accurate and reliable measurements of microphone coordinates. Manual measurements using digital range finders or measuring tapes do not provide sufficiently precise and reliable estimates of microphone positions, especially when used in natural conditions like vegetation or cave walls. The use of modern surveying tools such as a Total Station overcomes these difficulties and allows the time-efficient and accurate measurement of many microphone positions with a precision of a few millimeters. These measurements can then be used as input for the acoustic tracking software of choice, to then obtain reliable bat trajectories. However, for many biological questions, it is crucial to know the spatial context of the observed flight trajectories and calling behavior. Without a detailed quantitative map of the volume in which bats were flying in, it is hard to infer how environmental structures affected the observed flight paths and call design. This is another use case for modern geodetic tools such as LiDAR scanning. Having high-resolution 3D maps of an observation space, it is then possible to infer how the observed flight paths and call parameters were the result of obstacles such as rocks or narrow openings. In addition to just inferring the cause of behavior, it can also be used as a starting point for experimental manipulations (Goerlitz, Genzel, & Wiegrebe, 2012; Holderied, Jones, & Von Helvesen, 2006; Kong et al., 2016) and theoretical investigations in sensory and motor control (Schillebeeckx, De Mey, Vanderelst, & Peremans, 2011; Vanderelst, Holderied, & Peremans, 2015).

For our data collection of bat behavior, we used multi-channel acoustic recordings of 12-20 microphones synchronized with three thermal cameras. The cameras provided an independent source of 3D trajectory data to verify the path bats flew in the event of a noisy recording with multiple overlapping bat calls. The multi-channel audio-video recordings are currently undergoing analysis, and are the subject of further publications. The work was funded by Emmy Noether

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2. GEODETIC ACTIVITIES: METHODS AND RESULTS

The field geodetic activities were performed at two stages. First, conventional optical measurements were utilized to obtain precise Cartesian (XYZ) coordinates of the 12 wall-mounted microphones. This was done via a Trimble S6 Robotic total station (Fig. 4) on July 2018. All data was collected from a single geodetic marker, placed at a convenient location inside the echo sound recording chamber.

Figure 3. Laser scanner data collection

Figure 4. Total station measurements

The second stage, comprising the terrestrial laser scanning, was performed on the 18-19th August 2018 by a team from the University of Mining and Geology “St. Ivan Rilski”. A Stonex X300 laser scanner was utilized for that purpose. This is a lightweight mid-range (1.6 – 300 m) laser scanner, able to receive color and intensity information alongside three-dimensional data. It has a 32 GB internal memory, capable of storing up to 50 scans at maximum resolution (~700 MB each). The instrument has a built-in Wi-Fi interface, which was used for field setup via Android smartphone. The 3D geospatial dataset was obtained via 11 scans at maximum resolution (Fig. 5, Table 1). Since the cave chambers were not sufficiently lightened, color RGB data was not collected.

Figure 5. 2D representation of the 11 scans, colored by ID

Table 1. Stonex X300 data collection settings (full resolution mode)

Resolution	H. res. (360°)	V. res. (90°)	Total points	H. step (°)	V. step (°)	Time x 360°	Columns/sec.
Fine	16000	4000	64000000	1.350	1.350	1h 6m 40s	4

Some 20 paper targets were deployed temporarily around the cave for registration purpose. The area coverage as part of the total cave area is marked on Fig. 6.

Figure 6. Approximate area of the scanned entrance part of the cave (blue outline)

3. DATA PROCESSING

During data collection, all raw point cloud data were recorded in Stonex .x3a archive format. They were subsequently converted to Stonex .x3s grid (structured) point cloud, and imported into the Stonex 3D Reconstructor software (Educational edition), installed on a dedicated machine in UMG “St. Ivan Rilski”, with the following parameters: 64-bit OS, 16Gb RAM, Intel CORE i5, NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1060 6Gb. Several processing steps were incorporated:

3.1. Preprocessing

3.1.1. Noise removal

Three filtering techniques were applied:

- Range & Reflectance Gate - all pixels outside the instrument scanning range were filtered, plus all measurements with intensity values outside the [0-1] interval;
- Median filter
- Relative depth discontinuity filter

3.1.2. Computation of normals – a local surface tangent plane for each point was generated, based on the neighborhood of the pixel (local plane fitting);

3.1.3. Edge Detection – two types of geometrically significant line features from the point cloud data were computed: edge discontinuities (when there is a sudden change in the object orientation), and depth discontinuities (where the scanner hits an occlusion and therefore the measured range jumps from a foreground to a background value);

3.1.4. Confidence computation – a layer with a confidence value for each measurement (a measure for the reliability of the given range measurement) was generated, based on the incident angle between the laser beam and the tangent plane of the target, the distance to the target and the material of the object (respectively, the intensity of the reflected signal). The confidence value is computed as a weighted sum of the surface normal, the range value and the reflectance value (Gexcel s.r.l., 2008)

In addition, noise from tourists, bypassing the scanned area every now and then, was removed manually to a satisfactory degree using the cropping technique.

3.2. Registration

The preprocessed scans were registered manually via pairs of homologous points - paper targets, as well as distinctive cave features – info signs, lamps, natural objects. Every registration was performed via at least three homologous points, with RMS of less than 2 cm. After registration, all 11 point clouds were combined into a single cloud, and exported in ASCII (.txt) format, with the following columns: x,y,z,i (where i = intensity). The size of this point cloud file is above 12 Gb.

Since the model was to be used by the bat research crew in a local Cartesian coordinate system, georeferencing measurements were not involved in the project.

Figure 6. Paper targets (highlighted within the white indicator circle) deployment within the instrument range.

Figure 7. Visualization of the registered point clouds (numbers 1 to 4)

3.3. Mesh modeling

After preprocessing, noise clean up and registration, two different techniques for 3D mesh model generation were applied.

3.3.1. Interpolative technique

Two interpolative mesh-modelling techniques were attempted on the combined single point cloud:

- 2.5D Delaunay triangulation – this technique considers a rectangle including all points from the cloud, whose vertices are added to a mesh. Then triangulation is initialized using two triangles based on these points. Later for each edge node, a new node is added to a mesh and the triangulation is re-performed. The edges obtained between the 2D points are then applied to 3D space, leading to the so-called 2.5D triangulation (Rak, Mayer, and Woźniak, 2014). However, this approach, albeit promising the best results in terms of hole filling and cave surface approximation, was not able to be finished even for a single scan because of the tremendous CPU and RAM loading. All endeavors to perform this technique on the machine ended in critical error condition.
- Multiresolution modeling – a lighter computational method in the Stonex 3D Reconstructor software, in which the point cloud domain is divided into triangles and then Lagrange interpolation was applied to each. A triangle was created for a square wide $2^4=16$ pixels. If the approximation error was too high, the triangle was subdivided in smaller pieces. The 3D model is created by minimization of the sum of squared distances between the interpolated surface and the data points. A weighting strategy is applied by using less triangles on planar regions, satisfying an approximation error threshold. Results from this technique are visible in Figure 9.

Figure 8. 3D mesh model visualization of the recording chamber (multiresolution meshing technique)

3.3.2. Approximate technique

The second technique applied was the Poisson reconstruction approach - an approximate 3D meshing that does not need the input cloud to be structured. It estimates tangent planes and defines the implicit function as the signed distance to the tangent plane of the closest point (Kazhdan,

Bolitho, and Hoppe, 2006). Through this approach a connected, watertight triangulation surface that approximates the surface described by the points was reconstructed, taking as constraints the points' positions and orientations (normals). The meshing was performed with the “really many” triangles setting in the processing software. The setting for cloud smoothness was set to “moderate”. Closing holes and removing isolated components was performed automatically. Results from this technique are visible in Figure 10 and 11, loaded into the Autodesk Meshmixer software.

Figure 9 . 3D mesh model visualization of the recording chamber (Poisson reconstruction). Part of the bat recording equipment is visible in the right.

Figure 10 . 3D mesh model of the inner chambers (Poisson reconstruction)

3.4. Data export

The 3D mesh models, created via the two different techniques, were exported in .dxf and .ply formats, which (alongside the raw point cloud) are to be utilized by the bat researchers of the Acoustic and Functional Ecology Group at the MPI for Ornithology.

4. CONCLUSION

The executed work presents an interesting interdisciplinary direction at the interface of sensory biology and geodetics. The generated XYZ data from Total Station measurements and LiDAR scanning is going to form the basis of upcoming publications that are currently under preparation.

The 3D model may be utilized for various tasks, e.g. by the Rusenski Lom Nature Park authority for web-visualization purposes, or other research endeavors.

The project was performed at satisfactory level, considering the time limitation and the tourist stream during the recording period (weekend). A major consideration is the processing capacity of the machine, which hindered the generation of even more detailed 3D mesh model. Nevertheless, all data seem appropriate and adequate for further utilization in ornithology and other multidisciplinary projects.

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FEDERATION OF THE SCIENTIFIC ENGINEERING UNIONS
UNION OF SURVEYORS AND LAND MANAGERS
IN BULGARIA

CERTIFICATE

Herewith, we certify that

Asparuh Kamburov (BG), Holger Geurliz (DE), Thejasvi Beleyur (DE)

participated in the

XXVIII INTERNATIONAL SYMPOSIUM

ON

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President of the USLMB